

Higher Education Autonomy to Build Excellency with Responsibility and Accountability

P. S. Aithal¹ & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal^{2*}

¹Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India

²Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail : shubhbraaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Autonomy for higher educational institutions is essential for doing innovations in education implementing innovative courses, curriculum as per industry requirements, new knowledge creation by incorporating research components in the curriculum, etc. It is obvious that those organizations which use their autonomy with responsibility and accountability will certainly attain excellence. It is suggested that higher education institutions that have autonomy for doing innovations have to focus their attention on building their both tangible and intangible infrastructure called core-resource infrastructure for building Excellency. The six essential requirements identified based on our predictive analysis for the growth and prosper as world class universities are (1) Physical infrastructure, (2) Digital infrastructure, (3) Innovative academic & training Infrastructure for confidence building, (4) Intellectual property infrastructure, (5) Emotional infrastructure, and (6) Networked infrastructure. Institutions and universities who are poised to become World Class University with super specialty courses and student focussed Research programs will reach greater height through planning and developing such infrastructure. In this paper, various strategies to be planned and implemented in higher education institutions which have autonomy and intention to do innovations with responsibility and accountability are discussed.

Keywords : New directions in publications, Fearless innovations, Scholarly publications, Authors

1. INTRODUCTION :

Research is a process of developing new knowledge or new interpretation of existing knowledge in a systematic manner. Higher education institutions including universities have a responsibility towards the society to contribute to new knowledge by imparting research based courses in their service. Autonomy for higher educational institutions is essential for doing innovations in education implementing innovative courses, curriculum as per industry requirements, new knowledge creation by incorporating research components in the curriculum, etc. It is obvious that those organizations which use their autonomy with responsibility and accountability will certainly attain excellence. It is suggested that higher education institutions that have autonomy for doing innovations have to focus their attention

on building their both tangible and intangible infrastructure called core-resource infrastructure for building Excellency. The six essential requirements identified based on our predictive analysis for the growth and prosper as world class universities are (1) Physical infrastructure, (2) Digital infrastructure, (3) Innovative academic & training Infrastructure for confidence building, (4) Intellectual property infrastructure, (5) Emotional infrastructure, and (6) Networked infrastructure. Institutions and universities who are poised to become World Class University with super specialty courses and student focussed Research programs will reach greater height through planning and developing such infrastructure.

2. OBJECTIVES :

Innovations in higher education model are finding importance than ever before due to enhanced higher education institutions and the advancement in technology adopted mass education opportunities. The objectives this paper are :

- (1) To identify the essential infrastructures for autonomous institutions/ universities to attain Excellency in imparting higher education globally.
- (2) To determine the primary focus of these infrastructures along with their essentials in detail.
- (3) To study each infrastructure in detail and strategies to be followed to develop such infrastructures.
- (4) To discuss how the above Infrastructures help to develop strategies for Survival, Sustainability, Differentiation, and Growth & prosperity.

3. METHODOLOGY :

The methodology used in this study is called Focus group based Predictive analysis [x] which deals with collection of information related to identified problem from a group of experts in that and related fields and analysing such information in the context of predicting the future consequences of the identified present problem [7-9].

A simple method called predictive analysis is recently developed to address decision making problems related to predicting the future. Predictive analysis is an analytical method consisting of several techniques to predict future possibilities using present trends. It can be qualitative or quantitative. It is different from predictive analytics in such a way that it will support to predict future. On the other hand, predictive analytics is a method of generating information from historically available dataset to determine and predict future trends and outcomes [10].

Predictive analysis is a method consisting of several techniques to predict future possibilities using present trends. It is different from predictive analytics in such a way that it will support to predict future. On the other hand, predictive analytics is a method of generating information from historically available dataset to determine and predict future trends and outcomes. A qualitative predictive analysis is used to predict the future possibilities by studying present trends using self-developed predictive analysis model shown in figure 1 [11]. The procedure of predictive analysis of a system or an activity encompasses 4 steps : Collect information on present trends, Develop postulates based on present trends, Generate argument based description, and Predict the future.

Fig. 1 : Predictive Analysis Model to predict future [59]

4. ESSENTIALS FOR WORLD CLASS UNIVERSITIES :

The six infrastructures identified based on our predictive analysis for world class universities are listed in table 1 with their preliminary focus :

Table 1 : List of Infrastructures required for attaining excellence and their focus

S. No	Essentials for attaining Excellence	Primary Focus
1	Physical Infrastructure	Comfortability
2	Digital Infrastructure	Openness & Ubiquitous accessibility
3	Innovative academic Infrastructure	Confidence building
4	Intellectual Property Infrastructure	Creating new knowledge & Innovation
5	Emotional Infrastructure	Belongingness & Connectedness of all stakeholders
6	Industry Networked Infrastructure	Industry Interactions for Training, Placement, & entrepreneurship

Table 2 : Ideal Infrastructures required for attaining global excellence

S. No	Essentials for attaining Excellence	Ideal level
1	Physical Infrastructure	Open outdoor place without any disturbance
2	Digital Infrastructure	Free access to any & every information in any form
3	Innovative academic Infrastructure	Models and pedagogies to make ideal graduate with unlimited knowledge, skills, experience and hence confidence
4	Intellectual Property Infrastructure	Infinite ability to Creating new knowledge & new innovation (IP) by students & faculties.
5	Emotional Infrastructure	Every stakeholder feels that the organization is of his own and every other stakeholder is his family member.
6	Networked Infrastructure	Perfectly networked with all kind of industries in entire globe for open Placement & entrepreneurship

(1) Physical infrastructure :

Physical infrastructure is required to provide comfortability and safety for the stakeholders for the teaching-learning process. Though a good and safety physical infrastructure at a comfortable location is desired, the ideal education system promotes an Open outdoor place

without any disturbance. In reality the Country, Location, Land, Land connectivity, Landscaping, Students feeding area, Supporting industries, Attractive & green buildings, Structure & design of each buildings, Parking facilities, Roads with walking & bicycle path, Admission & Counselling Area, Classrooms, counselling rooms, faculty chambers, Meeting rooms, Laboratories, Studios, Gymnastics, Theatres, Cafeteria, Games & Sports facility, Auditorium, Library/Digital resource centre, Xerox & Printing centre, Hostels, Residents, Shops, Hospital, Student recreation facilities, International student centres, Research Park, etc. are considered essential components. Physical infrastructure provides comfort facilities to the stakeholders. It can be built for (1) minimum requirement with basic facilities to fulfil the objectives of higher education, or (2) for a fair level to satisfy the stakeholders and differentiate to gain competitive advantage, or (3) for a luxurious level to establish monopoly and high impact on stakeholders as mentioned in table 3.

Table 3 : List of Physical infrastructure Requirements for a University

S. No.	Facility	Area	Number of Units
Minimum Requirements			
1	Green building	Part of the Campus	-
2	Roads with walking, Motoring & bicycle path	Entre Campus buildings	-
3	Admission & Counselling Area	100 Sq. M.	3
4	Classrooms	120 student capacity	4
5	Classrooms	70 student capacity	6
6	Classrooms (Small)	30 student capacity	8
7	Counselling rooms	20 student capacity	6
8	Counselling rooms	12 student capacity	6
9	Strong Room	50 Sq.M.	01
10	Faculty chambers	12 Sq. M.	30
11	Meeting rooms	20 Participants	4
12	Laboratories	100 Sq. M.	4
13	Computer Centre	70 nodes	2
14	Cafeteria	150 people	1
15	Dining Room	10 People	2
16	Dining Room	30 People	1
17	Dining Room	90 People	1
18	Games & Sports facility	Indoor	1
19	Auditorium	300 capacity	1
20	Library/Digital resource centre	300 Sq. M.	01
21	Xerox & Printing centre	40 Sq. M	02
22	Hostels	1,000 students	02
23	Parking	200 Cars	02
24	Office Rooms	40 Sq. M.	04
25	Exhibition Hall	100 Sq. M.	02
26	Guest House	Adequate	-
Fair Requirements			
27	Faculty Residents	2 – 3 Bedrooms	As per requirement
28	Shops	2-3	As per requirement
29	Hospital	01	01

30	Student recreation facilities	Adequate	As per requirement
31	Yoga & Meditation Centre	Adequate	As per requirement
32	Faculty Cubical	Adequate	As per requirement
33	Departmental Libraries	Adequate	As per requirement
34	Students Waiting Room (Male)	50 Sq. M.	2-3
35	Student Waiting Room (Female)	50 Sq. M.	2-3
36	Faculty & Staff Quarters	1-2 Bedrooms	As per requirement
37	Guest Hostels	16 Sq. M.	20-30 inmates
38	Research Scholars Hostels	14 Sq. M/ Student	50
Luxury Requirements			
39	Central Air Conditioned High Tech Buildings	-	Adequate
40	Faculty Chamber with attached washroom for each faculty	16 Sq. M.	Adequate
41	Studios	100 Sq. M.	As per requirement
42	Gymnastics	100 Sq. M.	01
43	International student centres	200 Sq. M.	01
44	Research park	-	1-3
45	International Student Hostels	Adequate	As per requirement
46	High Tech Playgrounds	Adequate	As per requirement
47	Swimming Pool	400 Sq. M.	1-2
48	Shopping Complex	Adequate	1-2
49	Stadium	-	01
50	Indoor Stadium	-	1-2
51	Botanical Park	-	1

Even though, an appropriate physical infrastructure with adequate facilities is essential to attract admissions of students, it cannot offer a competitive advantage to the university continuously over a long time because competitors can also develop better infrastructure with more luxurious facilities to attract students and teachers to the system quickly by finding an appropriate investor. Physical infrastructure

(2) Digital infrastructure :

Internet usage, Website, WhatsApp groups for communication between Stakeholders : Vertical and horizontal communication, Google Blogs & Google sites for every course, Wi-Fi Campus, Online Study material, Digital Library, Digital Publication, Paperless office, Paperless exams, Online Evaluation, Website based result announcement, NDD marks cards, Online admission test, Education ERP, Plagiarism software facility, Online digital magazine & Student publication, Online placement (Project, internship, & final), Video documentation of each course & each College, Video documentation in U-Tube, Facebook and Twitter based promotions, Use of ICCT underlying technologies like AI, IOT, Cloud Computing, 3D Printing, etc.

(3) Innovative academic Infrastructure :

Industry oriented curriculum, Employability skill focussed curriculum, Speciality & super speciality professional courses, Experienced committed faculty, Session wise teaching plan, Studybook prepared as per the syllabus, Question bank, QB answers as assignments, Make-up exams, Value added employability skills enhancement Paper, Experimental learning

pedagogy, Co-curricular & extracurricular activities, Earn while learn facility & flexibility etc. are deciding factors.

(4) Intellectual property infrastructure :

Research oriented experience faculty members, API based faculty compensation, Targeted research, Atomic Research centres per faculty, More Ph.D. & post doctoral research scholars, More Faculty members with Ph.D., Encouragement for Book Publications, Research Publications and Patents, More conferences (At least two conferences per year per College), Student involvement in Research, Industry collaboration & Consultant, University Incubation centres & Publications, ABC model of Research productivity : Articles, Books, Case studies, & Patents, etc. are deciding factors.

(5) Emotional infrastructure :

Creating sense of belongingness with organization for all stakeholders. The elements are :

- (1) Acceptable leader as role-model
- (2) Trust among stakeholders and outsiders
- (3) Institutional values (Core values)
- (4) Institutional Rituals & Tradition
- (5) Create rich communication channels
- (6) Alternative strategy & Support network
- (7) Set vision in every student
- (8) Safety & Security
- (9) Search for proximity (Local friends. Local food, local culture)
- (10) Comfortability but need not luxury
- (11) Legacy of the system
- (12) Respect & perception about organization
- (13) Openness in terms of information
- (14) Accountability

(6) Networked infrastructure :

Collaborations – Horizontal, Vertical & Diversified, Alumni association & Networks, Industry integrated collaborations, Academic Integrated Collaborations, Research Collaborations, Consultancy Collaborations, etc. are deciding factors.

Table 4 : Infrastructural contribution corresponding to organizational strategy

S. No.	Organizational Strategy	Substantial Infrastructural Contribution
1	Survival	Physical & Emotional
2	Sustainability	Physical, IR, & Emotional
3	Differentiation	Physical, Digital, Academic, IR, Emotional
4	Growth & Prosperity	Physical, Digital, Academic, IR, Emotional, & Network

In general a necessary condition is a condition that must be present for an event to occur and a sufficient condition is essential to produce the event. In this line it is argued that the physical, digital, and academic infrastructures are *Necessary conditions* and IR, Emotional, and Network infrastructures are *Sufficient conditions* for creating World –class infrastructure.

Table 5 : Necessary and sufficient conditions of different infrastructures

S. No.	Conditions	Substantial Infrastructural Contribution
1	Necessary Conditions	Physical, Digital & Academic
2	Sufficient Conditions	Intellectual Property, Emotional, and Network with Industries

Table 6 : Relation between organizational strategy and their contribution

S. No.	Organizational Strategy	Substantial Infrastructural Contribution
1	Survival	Physical & Emotional
2	Sustainability	Physical, IR, & Emotional
3	Differentiation	Physical, Digital, Academic, IR, Emotional
4	Growth & Prosperity	Physical, Digital, Academic, IR, Emotional, & Network

5. CONCLUSION :

It is suggested that higher education institutions that have autonomy for doing innovations have to focus their attention on building their both tangible and intangible infrastructure called core-resource infrastructure for building Excellency. The six essential requirements identified based on our predictive analysis for the growth and prosper as world class universities are (1) Physical infrastructure, (2) Digital infrastructure, (3) Innovative academic & training Infrastructure for confidence building, (4) Intellectual property infrastructure, (5) Emotional infrastructure, and (6) Networked infrastructure. Institutions and universities who are poised to become World Class University with super specialty courses and student focussed Research programs will reach greater height through planning and developing such infrastructure.

REFERENCES:

[1] Aithal, P. S., & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2019). Building World-class Universities : Some Insights & Predictions. Under publication in *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 4(1).

[2] Aithal, P. S., & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2019). Strategies proposed Autonomous Higher Education Institutions and Universities based on Life-Cycle model. Under publication in *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 2(1).

[3] Aithal P. S., Anil Kumar, Madhushree, & Revathi R. (2018). Investigation of Business Strategies in Higher Education Service Model of Selected Private Universities in India. *International Journal of Computational Research and Development (IJCRD)*, 3(1), 2018, 77-100. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1209910>.

[4] Aithal, P. S., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Teaching - Learning Process in Higher Education Institutions. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education (IJMRME)*, 2(1) pp. 662-676. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160956>.

- [5] Aithal, P. S., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Maintaining Teacher Quality in Higher Education Institutions, *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 701-711. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160946>.
- [6] Aithal, P. S., and Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Student performance and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education Institutions, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1) 674 – 684. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160944>.
- [7] Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Student Evaluation and Reforms in Higher Education Institutions, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education (IJMRME)*, 2(1), 652-661, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160932>.
- [8] Aithal, P. S., Srinivas Rao, A. & Suresh Kumar, P.M. (2015). How Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions : A case study of SIMS. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 6(2), 83 - 98, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61594>.
- [9] Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2015). An Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 3(3), 2464 - 2469, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61654>.
- [10] Aithal, P. S., Srinivas Rao, A. & P.M. Suresh Kumar, (2015). Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions : A case study of SIMS. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 2(5), 18-31. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.266940>.
- [11] Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities in India. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 88-113, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161157>.
- [12] Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2017). Opportunities for Enhancing Research & Publications in Higher Education, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education*, 2(1), 42-49.
- [13] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.
- [14] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>.
- [15] Altbach, P. (2015). The costs and benefits of world-class universities. *International Higher Education*, (33).
- [16] Altbach, P. G., & Salmi, J. (Eds.). (2011). *The road to academic excellence: The making of world-class research universities*. The World Bank.
- [17] Wang, Q., Cheng, Y., & Liu, N. C. (Eds.). (2013). *Building world-class universities: Different approaches to a shared goal*(Vol. 25). Springer Science & Business Media.

- [18] Byun, K., Jon, J. E., & Kim, D. (2013). Quest for building world-class universities in South Korea: Outcomes and consequences. *Higher Education*, 65(5), 645-659.
- [18] Wang, Q. H., Wang, Q., & Liu, N. C. (2011). Building world-class universities in China: Shanghai Jiao Tong University.
- [20] Salmi, J. (2009). *The challenge of establishing world class universities*. The World Bank.
- [21] Huang, F. (2015). Building the world-class research universities: A case study of China. *Higher Education*, 70(2), 203-215.
- [22] Cheng, Y., Wang, Q., & Liu, N. C. (2014). How world-class universities affect global higher education. In *How World-Class Universities Affect Global Higher Education* (pp. 1-10). SensePublishers, Rotterdam.
- [23] Kottke, J. L. (1999). Corporate universities: Lessons in building a world-class work force (revised). *Personnel Psychology*, 52(2), 530.
- [24] Krishnan, R. T. (2005). Building World Class Universities. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 1681-1683.
- [25] Montesinos, P., Carot, J. M., Martinez, J. M., & Mora, F. (2008). Third mission ranking for world class universities: Beyond teaching and research. *Higher education in Europe*, 33(2-3), 259-271.
- [26] Deng, Q., Wang, Q., & Liu, N. C. (2010). National initiatives for building world-class universities: comparison between Asian and European experiences. *Research Institute for Higher Education Hiroshima University*, 7, 735.
- [27] Salmi, J. (2010). The challenge of establishing world-class research universities in developing countries. *University Research for Innovation*, 271.
- [28] Hou, A. Y. C., Morse, R., & Chiang, C. L. (2012). An analysis of mobility in global rankings: making institutional strategic plans and positioning for building world-class universities. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 31(6), 841-857.
- [29] Shen, G. (2015). Building world-class universities in China: From the view of national strategies. *The Global University Network for Innovation* URL: www.guninetwork.org/resources/he-articles/building-world-class-universities-inchina-from-the-view-of-national-strategie.
- [30] Oba, J. (2008). Creating world-class universities in Japan: Policy and initiatives. *Policy Futures in Education*, 6(5), 629-640.
- [31] Salmi, J. (2016). Excellence strategies and the creation of world-class universities. In *Matching Visibility and Performance* (pp. 15-48). SensePublishers, Rotterdam.
- [32] Lee, J. (2013). Creating world-class universities: Implications for developing countries. *Prospects*, 43(2), 233-249.
- [33] Altbach, P. (2015). India: World-Class Universities?. *International Higher Education*, (40).

- [34] Salmi, J. (2013). Can Young Universities Achieve World-Class Status?. *International Higher Education*, (70), 2-3.
- [35] Bejinaru, R., & Prelipcean, G. (2017, July). Successful strategies to be learnt from world-class universities. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence* (Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 350-358). De Gruyter Open.